

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

ANALYSIS OF THE DYNAMICS OF INCOME AND COSTS OF THE POPULATION IN THE REPUBLIC OF AZERBAIJAN

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ABSTRACT

In the presented work, a statistical analysis of the distribution of income indicators and costs of the population was carried out, the distribution of the population's income and the degree of stratification of the society were investigated based on the Gini and Lorenz indices. An extensive empirical analysis of the time series according to the income and costs indicators of the population was carried out, descriptive statistics were determined, the normal distribution of the series based on the Jarque-Bera test, stationarity was investigated based on the autocorrelation function and the Dickey-Fuller test, White, Cusum tests were checked. AR models with first and second order differences were established, it was determined that the AR(1) model for income is not stationary, the AR(2) model satisfies the stationarity conditions, and the AR(1) time series for costs is stationary.

The conducted research can be evaluated as the basis of studies on extensive empirical analysis, modeling and forecasting of the income and cost of the population in the Republic of Azerbaijan and create wide opportunities for prospective studies. The statistical information used in the study was obtained from the official website of the State Statistical Institute and covers the years 1995-2021. The obtained data were processed in Excel and Eviews application software packages.

Keywords: empirical analysis of income and cost indicators of the population, Jarque-Bera test, AR models, Cusum test, autocorrelation, stationarity.

Introduction. In modern periods, the statistical study of the income and costs of the population across countries is of great importance. Accordingly, to analyze the standard of living of the population, to develop a socio-economic policy and, most importantly, to organize the social protection of individual population groups, it is necessary to collect and statistical analyze objective data about income. Income is an important economic indicator reflecting social development. If the distribution of income is fair, the social welfare in the country will increase, the poverty level will decrease and there will be optimistic expectations about the future. Currently, the change in the economic situation in a number of countries has a significant impact on the living standards of the population and its separate strata, as well as the level and structure of their income and costs to one degree or another. The population's standard of living has seriously decreased, the number of unemployed and those living in poverty has increased, the process of stratification has intensified, such cases increase the importance of the statistical study of income and expenses of the population based on the MHS concept, justifies the relevance of the topic of the research.

It is important to collect objective information about the income and costs of the population, to analyze the general state of the economy and the standard of living of the population, to develop the social policy of the state and to implement concrete measures to organize. Systematized information on the income of the

population can be used to assess the possibilities of expanding investment processes through the mobilization of internal resources. Despite the statistical analysis, modeling of macroeconomic indicators [5,14] that shape and determine the standard of living of the population in domestic and foreign literature [3,4,7,9,16,17], as well as work designed to investigate and solve other problems, the relevance of the issue considered, the application of these economic for research studies is important [1,2,6,12,13].

A number of scientific articles are devoted to these problems, taking into account regional characteristics in the process of transformation of national economies, and are devoted to the analysis of integration processes between individual countries and groups of countries of the post-Soviet space.

The main part of research. The statistical data required to conduct an econometric analysis of the uneven distribution of income and cost of the population in the Republic of Azerbaijan were obtained from the official website[15] of the State Statistical Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan and presented in Table 1. The statistical information in Table 1 indicates *Income (Y1)* - the income of the population, *Absolute rate of change (Y2)* - the rate of absolute change of income, *Costs (Y3)* - the cost of the population. The absolute rate of change of income was determined by calculating the ratio of the difference between the current level and the previous level to the previous level according to the income in the Excel software package.

Table 1.

Income and cost indicators of the population for the years 1995-2021 (in current prices, in million manats)

Years	Income(Y1)	Absolute rate of change (Y2)	Costs (Y3)
1995	1,340.5	-	1,275.8
1996	1,905.1	0.42	1,853.1
1997	2,473.4	0.30	2,411.3
1998	2,884.8	0.17	2,932.6
1999	3,687.7	0.28	3031.4
2000	4,047.3	0.10	3,272.2
2001	4,301.6	0.06	3,498.4
2002	5,018.6	0.17	4,171.2
2003	5,738.1	0.14	4,793.8
2004	6,595.1	0.15	5,549.9
2005	8,063.6	0.22	6,508.7
2006	10,198.5	0.26	8,208.1
2007	14,558.2	0.43	11,249.7
2008	20,735.4	0.42	15,891.9
2009	22,601.1	0.09	17,417.6
2010	25,607.0	0.13	19,251.5
2011	30,524.6	0.19	22,184.0
2012	34,769.5	0.14	24,564.0
2013	37,562.0	0.08	28,021.2
2014	39,472.2	0.05	30,799.6
2015	41,744.8	0.06	34,963.4
2016	45,395.1	0.09	39,775.0
2017	49,187.9	0.08	44,498.4
2018	53,103.7	0.08	47,557.2
2019	56,769.0	0.07	51,927.4
2020	55,754.1	-0.02	49,744.0
2021	57,181.5	0.03	55201.5

Source: Prepared by the authors based on the data obtained from the State Statistical Committee.

The results of descriptive statistics are important in time series analysis.

Table 2.

Results of descriptive statistics on incomes and costs of the population, absolute rate of change of income

	Income (Y1) (23748.90)	Absolute rate of change(Y2) (0.161280)	Costs (Y3) (20020.48)
Median	20735.40	0.136031	15891.90
Maximum	57181.50	0.427484	55201.50
Minimum	1340.500	-0.017878	1275.800
Std.Dev	20260.34	0.123748	18141.79
Skewness	0.395810	0.970919	0.644498
Kurtosis	1.619909	3.022570	1.981182
Jarque-Bera statistic	2.847730	4.085511	3.036940
Probability	0.240782	0.129671	0.219047
Sum	641220.4	4.193279	540552.9
Sum Sq.Dev	1.07E+10	0.382837	8.56E+09
Observations	27	26	27

In Table 2 represents average indicators, mean square deviations, excess, asymmetry and other characteristics of time series on income, absolute rate of change of income and costs. Satisfactory results were obtained for all three series for both excess and asymmetry. In this way, for these mentioned characteristics, the calculated results in all cases are small and very close to 0, they satisfy the conditions for the significance of asymmetry and excess. The distribution of the time series follows a normal distribution in all three cases. The results of the Jarque-Bera test also confirm this. $JB_{Y1}=2.847730$, $prob.=0.240>0.05$; since

$JB_{Y2}=4.085511$, $prob.=0.12>0.05$ and $JB_{Y3}=3.036940$, $prob.=0.21>0.05$, the hypotheses of normal distribution are accepted. Note that the average values for Y1, Y2 and Y3 are listed in parentheses in Table 2.

Results according to the autocorrelation function (ACF) and specific autocorrelation function (PACF), their graphs and the results of the ADF test with both primary and first and second order differences can characterize the stationarity of time series [8,10,11,14]. In the next step of the research, the autocorrelation functions for the incomes and costs of the population were investigated.

The presence of autocorrelation among the residuals in the autoregression model indicates that there is correlation between the levels of the time series. This dependence causes cyclical fluctuations in the levels of the series, which leads to the low quality and inefficiency of the forecasts formed on the basis of the autoregression model, because deviations of a cyclical nature, in general, are not random and can create a trend. The analysis of dynamic results and the

constructed autocorrelation and special autocorrelation functions of the considered time series can form an opinion whether the series $Y1$ and $Y3$ are stationary or non-stationary according to the initial data.

Thus, in the autocorrelation analysis conducted on population incomes, probabilities less than 0.05 for all levels determine that the series is non-stationary, and the H_0 hypothesis is rejected (see Picture 1).

Sample: 1995 2021

Included observations: 26

Picture 1. ACF and PACF for the order $Y1$ according to the income of the population.

In picture 2 presents the results of the autocorrelation analysis on population costs. In this case, the probabilities are equal to 0.00 for all levels of the series, and the hypothesis H_1 is accepted as an alternative hypothesis to H_0 about the non-stationarity of the considered series.

Sample: 1995 2021

Included observations: 27

Picture 2. ACF and PACF for the $Y3$ row according to population cost.

According to the results in Picture-1 and Picture-2, we can conclude that ACF decreases for series $Y1$ and $Y3$, and PACF has the highest autocorrelation coefficient for series $Y1$ for first order and for series $Y3$ for first and third order. Functions for other levels do not have significant autocorrelation coefficients.

In the conducted research, the capabilities of the *Dickey-Fuller* test were used to eliminate the non-stationarity of the studied time series based on the

primary data. Let's examine the *ADF* test results using the Eviews application software package. According to the test, the hypothesis that the time series has a single root is accepted if the probability of the t-statistic is less than 5% (significance level of 0.05). For the time series to be stationary, the value of the *Dickey-Fuller* test should be smaller than the critical value at the 1%, 5%, 10% significance levels. The test results are presented in Table 3:

Table 3.

Dickey-Fuller test results					
Variable	T-statistic	Critical values: 1%	Critical values: 5%	Critical values: 10%	Prob.
First difference, trend and constant					
<i>Income (Y1)</i>	-2.666340	-4.374307	-3.603202	-3.238054	0.2573
<i>Absolute rate of change (Y2)</i>	-5.152159	-4.416345	-3.622033	-3.248592	0.0021
<i>Costs (Y3)</i>	-5.217134	-4.374307	-3.603202	-3.238054	0.0015
Second difference, trend and constant					
<i>Income (Y1)</i>	-5.170003	-4.416345	-3.622033	-3.248592	0.0020
<i>Absolute rate of change (Y2)</i>	-7.392002	-4.440739	-3.632896	-3.254671	0.0000
<i>Costs (Y3)</i>	-9.236511	-4.394309	-3.612199	-3.243079	0.0000

In Table 3, because the probability level for *Income (Y1)* is greater than 0.05, the time series is trending and stationary with the first difference, and the absolute rate of change of income (*Y2*) is less than 0.05, and the t-statistic value is 1% , 5%, is smaller than the significance level value of 10%, so the H_0 -hypothesis is rejected and the time series is stationary in the case of trend constant with the first difference. When we look at cost (*Y3*), since the probability level is less than 0.05, and also the value of t-statistic is smaller than the value of 1%, 5%, 10% significance level, the time series is assumed to be stationary in the case of trend constant with first order difference. The probability level of *Income (Y1)* with the second design difference is less than 0.05 and the value of the t-statistic is smaller than the value of the significance level of 1%, 5%, 10%, so the H_0 -hypothesis is rejected and the trend with the second design differences is stationary. Since the absolute rate of change of income (*Y2*) is smaller than

the 5% probability level and the 1%, 5%, 10% significance level, the second formulation is considered stationary in the case of a trend constant with the difference, and also the cost (*Y3*) is less than the 5% probability level and the 1%, 5%, 1%, 5%, since it is smaller than the 10% significance level, the second formulation is stationary with the trend constant.

White's test was used to check the heteroskedasticity and the result is given in Table-4 for income, Table-5 for absolute rate of change of income, and Table-6 for cost. $nR^2=Obs*R^2$, the number of observations was taken $n=26$ in both cases. It received value $R^2=3.506367$ for income, $R^2=1.264556$ for absolute rate of change of income, and $R^2=4.729267$ for cost. As the probability level for all three values is greater than 0.05, heteroscedasticity is not detected in the model, and the hypothesis H_0 about homoscedasticity is accepted.

Table 4.

White test results (<i>Income Y1</i>)			
F-statistic	1.792650	Prob (2,23)	0.1890
Obs*R- squared	3.506367	Prob. Chi-Square (2)	0.1732

Table 5.

White test results (<i>Absolute rate of change Y2</i>)			
F-statistic	0.587917	Prob(2,23)	0.5636
Obs*R- squared	1.264556	Prob. Chi-Square (2)	0.5314

Table 6.

White test results (<i>Costs Y3</i>)			
F-statistic	2.548241	Prob(2,24)	0.0992
Obs*R- squared	4.729267	Prob.Chi-Square(2)	0.0940

It is used to evaluate the stability of the parameters of the model. These tests are based on the calculation of the cumulative sum of the recursive residuals and the cumulative sum of the squares of the recursive residuals and the evaluation of the corresponding equations. Test results are analyzed according to 95% confidence intervals. If the recursive estimates of the residuals deviate from the critical limits, then this indicates instability of the model parameters. Graphically, if the

blue line is located between the red lines and does not intersect with them, it confirms the H_0 hypothesis about the stability of the parameters, otherwise, if the blue line intersects with the red lines, then the H_1 hypothesis about the instability of the parameters relative to the length of the time interval is accepted. The results of the *CUSUM* test are shown in Picture-3 for income, Picture-4 for the absolute rate of change of income, and Picture-5 for cost.

Picture 3. Cusum test and standardized residuals (income Y1)

Picture 4. Cusum test and standardized residuals (Absolute rate of change Y2)

Picture 5. Cusum test and standardized residuals (costs Y3)

According to the results of the *CUSUM* test for the income of the population (*Y1*), the instability of its parameter is observed because it does not meet the required conditions. As the level indicators of the results of the *CUSUM* test on the absolute rate of change of income (*Y2*) are close to each other, they do not change and give the impression of stable dynamics on a straight line, and since the blue line is located between the red lines, it is assumed that the *Y2*-parameter is stable or steady. Also presented in Picture

4 is a representation of the standardized residuals, and in this graphical representation, the recursive values of residuals (*CUSUM*) and the recursive values of squares of residuals (*CUSUM of Squares*) do not deviate from the 95% confidence interval. According to the results of the *CUSUM* test on cost (*Y3*) in figure 5, the cost parameters can be considered stable and steady.

Let's consider autoregression models with first and second order differences to characterize the dependencies between economic indicators.

Table 7.

Autoregression model with first-order differences for population income

Summary Output					
Regression Statistics					
Multiple R	0.997215				
R Square	0.994437				
Adjusted R Square	0.993603				
Standard Error	1587.557				
Observations	24				
ANOVA					
	df	SS	MS	F	SignificanceF
Regression	3	9.01E+09	3E+09	1191.807	1.05E-22
Residual	20	50406745	2520337		
Total	23	9.06E+09			

	Coefficients	Stan.Error	t Statistic	P-value	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	Lower 95.0%	Upper 95.0%
Intercept	1066.53	598.5724	1.7817895	0.089975	-182.07	2315.13	-182.07	2315.13
Lag1	1.570632	0.22444	6.998013	8.63E-07	1.10245	2.03880	1.1024	2.03880
Lag2	-0.670945	0.444032	-1.51103	0.14642	-1.5971	0.25528	-1.597	0.25528
Lag3	0.108678	0.299961	0.362305	0.720924	-0.5170	0.73438	-0.517	0.73438

Based on the results presented in Table 7, the formal autoregression model of the population income dynamics with first order differences is as follows:

$$YI(t) = 1066.53 + 1.570632 * YI(t-1)$$

For the studied process to be stationary, the roots of the corresponding characteristic equation must be

outside the unit circle. The characteristic equation for the AR(1) model is: $1 - 1.5706z = 0$. The root of the equation is equal to $z \approx 0.637$, that is,

$|z| < 1$. For the AR(1) model, the process is non-stationary. This is confirmed by the results of our previous research for YI .

Table 8.

Autoregression model of population income with second-order differences

Summary Output					
Regression Statistics					
Multiple R	0.997196				
R Square	0.994401				
Adjusted R Square	0.993868				
Standard Error	1554.373				
Observations	24				
ANOVA					
	df	SS	MS	F	SignificanceF
Regression	2	9.01E+09	4.51E+09	1864.787	2.27E-24
Residual	21	50737577	2416075		
Total	23	9.06E+09			

	Coefficients	Stan.Error	t Statistic	P-value	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	Lower 95.0%	Upper 95.0%
Intercept	1022.096	573.6271	1.781812	0.089975	-170.82	2215.01	-170.82	2215.01
Lag1	1.530951	0.191807	7.981716	8.54E-08	1.132065	1.92983	1.1320	1.92983
Lag2	-0.52794	0.199139	-2.65112	0.01494	-0.94207	-0.1138	-0.942	-0.1138

Based on the results in Table 8, the autoregression model of the population income dynamics with second-order differences is described by the following equation:

$$YI(t) = 1022.096 + 1.530951YI(t-1) - 0.52794YI(t-2)$$

Characteristic equation for the AR(2) model $1 - 1.53z - 0.527z^2 = 0$. The roots of the equation are $z_1 \approx 2.34$, $z_2 \approx -5.24$. From this we can conclude that the AR(2) model is stationary with second order differences.

Table 9.

Autoregression model of population costs with first-order differences

Summary Output								
Regression Statistics								
Multiple R	0.99597							
R Square	0.991957							
Adjusted R Square	0.990687							
Standard Error	1727.656							
Observations	23							
ANOVA								
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>			
Regression	3	6.99E+09	2.33E+09	781.0782	4.55E-20			
Residual	19	56711135	2984796					
Total	22	7.05E+09						

	Coefficients	Stan.Error	t Statistic	P-value	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	Lower 95.0%	Upper 95.0%
Intercept	926.7874	640.409022	1.44718	0.164145	-413.604	2267.179	-413.604	2267.179
Lag1	0.899451	0.23039143	3.904013	0.000954	0.417236	1.381666	0.417236	1.381666
Lag2	0.867129	0.5375847	1.613009	0.123229	-0.25805	1.992307	-0.25805	1.992307
Lag3	-0.77357	0.44574376	-1.73547	0.098849	-1.70653	0.15938	-1.70653	0.15938

Based on the results of Table 9, the autoregression model with differences of order 1 for population expenditure is described as follows:

$$Y3(t) = 926.7874 + 0.899451 * Y3(t-1)$$

The characteristic equation for the cost AR(1) model is: $1 - 0.8994z = 0$. The root of the equation: $z \approx 1.118$, that is $|z| > 1$, so the process is stationary with first-order differences.

The most popular methods for analyzing the dynamics of population income are the application of the Lorenz curve and the Gini coefficient. The Gini coefficient takes a value between 0 and 1, if the result is close to 1, the inequality in the distribution of income is high, and when the index approaches 0, it shows that there is an equal distribution in the distribution of income.

Table 10.

Results according to the Gini coefficient (1995-2021)

<i>Individual</i>	<i>Income</i>	<i>Cumulative</i>		<i>Cumulative %of income</i>	<i>Area Under</i>	<i>Lorenz Curve</i>
		<i>%of population</i>	<i>%of income</i>			
1	1340.5	3.7037037	0.20905448	0.20905448	0.003871	0.00387138
2	1905.1	7.4074074	0.29710533	0.50615982	0.013244	0.01324471
3	2473.4	11.1111111	0.3857332	0.89189302	0.025889	0.02588987
4	2884.8	14.8148148	0.44989211	1.34178513	0.04136441	0.04136441
5	3687.7	18.5185185	0.57510647	1.9168916	0.06034587	0.06034587
6	4047.3	22.2222222	0.63118703	2.54807863	0.08268463	0.08268463
7	4301.6	25.9259259	0.67084578	3.21892441	0.10679635	0.10679635
8	5018.6	29.6296296	0.78266381	4.00158822	0.1337132	0.1337132
9	5738.1	33.3333333	0.89487172	4.89645994	0.16477867	0.16477867
10	6595.1	37.037037	1.02852311	5.92498305	0.20039709	0.20039709
11	8063.6	40.7407407	1.25753953	7.18252258	0.24273159	0.24273159
12	10198.5	44.4444444	1.59048277	8.77300535	0.29547274	0.29547274
13	14558.2	48.1481481	2.2703894	11.0433948	0.36697037	0.36697037
14	20735.4	51.8518519	3.23373991	14.2771347	0.46889869	0.46889869
15	22601.1	55.5555556	3.52470071	17.8018354	0.594055	0.594055
16	25607	59.2592593	3.99347869	21.7953141	0.73328055	0.73328055
17	30524.6	62.962963	4.76039128	26.5557053	0.89538925	0.89538925
18	34769.5	66.6666667	5.42239455	31.9780999	1.08395936	1.08395936
19	37562	70.3703704	5.85789223	37.8359921	1.29285356	1.29285356
20	39472.2	74.0740741	6.15579292	43.991785	1.51532921	1.51532921
21	41744.8	77.7777778	6.51021084	50.5019959	1.74988483	1.74988483
22	45395.1	81.4814815	7.07948468	57.5814806	2.00154586	2.00154586
23	49187.9	85.1851852	7.67098177	65.2524623	2.27470265	2.27470265
24	53103.7	88.8888889	8.28166103	73.5341234	2.57012196	2.57012196
25	55754.1	92.5925926	8.69499785	82.2291212	2.88450453	2.88450453
26	56769	96.2962963	8.85327416	91.0823954	3.20947253	3.20947253
27	57181.5	100	8.91760462	100	3.53856288	3.53856288
Sum	641220.4				Sum	26.5508217
Area A			23.4491783			
Gini index			0.46898357			0.037037037

Source: Calculated in the Excel software package based on the data obtained from the State Statistical Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan

According to the calculations made in the Excel software package, the *Gini index* is equal to 0.46898, and the population income distribution and the degree of social stratification based on the Lorenz indices are graphically presented in Picture 6.

Picture 6. Lorenz curve

The dependence between the incomes of the population and the accumulated frequencies for the population is presented in Picture 6. The Lorenz curve (dotted curve) is slightly away from the line of equal distribution of incomes (straight line), showing that there is no high level of concentration in the distribution of incomes, and that a trend is followed at an average level. This shows the partial adequacy of the ratio between the income received by the population and the share of income by population groups. Thus, 26.5% of the population of the region receives an income below the subsistence minimum. Also, considering that the Gini coefficient in Azerbaijan is 0.46 for the years 1995-2021, we can say that the income distribution is at an average level.

Main results:

1. Based on the information obtained from the State Statistical Committee, a statistical analysis of the distribution of income and expenses of the population in the Republic of Azerbaijan for the years 1995-2021 was carried out.

2. Empirical analysis of the time series according to the income and cost indicators of the population was carried out, descriptive statistics, *ACF* and *PACF* were determined, *Jarque-Bera*, *Dickey-Fuller*, *White*, *Cusum* tests were checked. Normal distribution in time series Y_1 , Y_2 , Y_3 according to *Jarque-Bera* test, non-stationarity of income and cost time series according to primary data according to *ACF* and *PACF*, second-order differences in income according to *ADF* test, first-order differences of absolute rate of change in income and expenses stationarity was determined in the case of trend constant with first and second order differences. The *Cusum* test demonstrated the stability of Y_2 and Y_3 parameters.

3. Autoregression models with first and second order differences were formed for the incomes and costs of the population, the AR model for incomes with

second order differences, and for expenses with first order differences fulfilled the stationarity conditions and demonstrated adequacy.

4. The degree of social stratification of the society was characterized by the Gini index and the Lorenz equilibrium curve. The Gini coefficient was calculated and the results were depicted in a graph, and based on the available data, an absolute equilibrium curve was constructed, which visually shows the degree of stratification of the society, using the Lorenz curve with the appropriate approximation function, and the formation of a trend at the average level of income distribution was determined.

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